

Novel Cosine Similarity Measures for Interval-Valued Fermatean Neutrosophic Sets with TOPSIS-Based MCDM Applications

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Abstract. In the evolving realm of decision science, accurately measuring similarity under uncertainty is paramount. This paper proposes three novel CSMs between IVFNS based on vector-based analysis, distance functions, and cosine functions. Mathematical properties such as boundedness, symmetry, and identity are proven for each proposed measure, ensuring their theoretical soundness. To improve flexibility in MCDM, we also propose weighted extensions of these measures. The IVFNS improves traditional Fermatean neutrosophic sets by introducing interval-valued truth, falsity, and indeterminacy. These enhancements enable more effective modeling of partial ignorance and uncertainty, especially when data is vague or imprecise. Furthermore, the study integrates the proposed CSMs into a TOPSIS-based MCDM framework under the IVFNS environment. The effectiveness, accuracy, and consistency of the approach are demonstrated through three real-world applications: pattern recognition, medical diagnosis, and international financial investment in five innovative start-ups. A comprehensive numerical example, complemented by comparative analysis, illustrates that the proposed approach outperforms existing methods in uncertain decision environments.

Keywords: Interval-valued Fermatean neutrosophic sets, cosine similarity measures, TOPSIS method, multi criteria decision making.

1. Introduction

MCDM is an essential tool for evaluating and selecting the optimum set of alternatives based on multiple and diverse criteria simultaneously. It plays a critical role in real-world complexities. The traditional DM methods assume deterministic inputs, but most real-world problems involve uncertainty, vagueness, and subjective assessments. To address this

TABLE 1. Nomenclature

<i>FS</i>	<i>Fuzzy Set</i>
<i>IFS</i>	<i>Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set</i>
<i>IVIFS</i>	<i>Interval - Valued Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set</i>
<i>PFS</i>	<i>Pythagorean Fuzzy Set</i>
<i>IVPS</i>	<i>Interval - Valued Pythagorean Set</i>
<i>FFS</i>	<i>Fermatean Fuzzy Set</i>
<i>CIFS</i>	<i>Cubic Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set</i>
<i>NS</i>	<i>Neutrosophic Set</i>
<i>IVNS</i>	<i>Interval - Valued Neutrosophic Set</i>
<i>FNS</i>	<i>Fermatean Neutrosophic Set</i>
<i>IVFNS</i>	<i>Interval - Valued Fermatean Neutrosophic Set</i>
<i>CSM</i>	<i>Cosine Similarity Measure</i>
<i>MCDM</i>	<i>Multi Criteria Decision Making</i>

imprecise information, Zadeh [32] introduced the concept of FS theory to represent the data in membership degrees rather than the crisp values. Over time, several extensions, such as IFS [4], IVIFS [5], PFS [31], and FFS [28], have been developed and incorporated into MCDM frameworks. Previous models like FS and IFS addressed uncertainty but failed to capture indeterminacy and inconsistency fully. To overcome this, neutrosophic sets were introduced by Smarandache [26], allowing independent truth, falsity, and indeterminacy degrees, enabling more comprehensive modeling of uncertainty and partial truth in complex systems. Later, Smarandache [27] generalizes IFS and paraconsistent sets into neutrosophic sets, highlighting distinctions between NS and IFS with illustrative examples.

In the contemporary era of data-intensive research and analytical modeling, the evaluation of relational proximity between data entities has become a critical concern. Similarity measures provide a precise mathematical basis for comparing objects and are widely used in fields like medical diagnostics, image processing, and decision-making. A CSM based on Bhattacharyya [6] distance and subsequently refined by Salton and McGill (1983 [22]) can be characterized as the ratio of the dot product of two vectors to the product of their magnitudes. TOPSIS, proposed by Hwang and Yoon [10] in 1981, is a widely recognized MCDM method designed to rank alternatives based on their closeness to an ideal and distance from a negative-ideal solution. Jun Ye [11] proposed a CSM for IFS, representing it as a two-dimensional vector defined by its membership and non-membership degrees, while disregarding the degree of hesitation. Singh [25] and Jun Ye [12] contributed significantly

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to the development of CSMs, focusing on IVIFSs. An SM for IVIFS is proposed using midpoints of transformed triangular fuzzy numbers and applied to medical diagnosis and pattern recognition problems by Dhivya and Sridevi [8]. The previous studies did not consider the middle and boundary points of the intervals. To address this limitation, Premalatha & Dhanalakshmi [15] proposed an enhanced CSM for IVIFS and applied it in the TOPSIS method. Saranya et al. [23] introduced a computationally efficient CSM for CIFS, incorporating vector-based and distance-based formulations with proven mathematical properties, and demonstrated its superiority in decision-making applications such as pattern recognition and medical diagnosis. A TOPSIS-based MCDM approach within the CIFS framework using CSMs was developed to effectively address uncertainty through a validated financial investment case study by Saranya et al. [24].

To address the limitations in capturing indeterminacy and inconsistency, Broumi and Smarandache [18] develop similarity measures for NS based on the Hausdorff distance and introduce a new measure to quantify their degree of similarity and also prove necessary properties of these measures. Building on this, the IVNS was proposed by Wang et al. [29], extending truth, indeterminacy, and false memberships to interval values and proving various properties and convexity to enhance the modeling of uncertainty and inconsistency. Wang et al. [30] developed a single-valued neutrosophic set (SVNS) and studied set-theoretic operators and related properties. Arunodaya Mishra et al. [2] propose a novel SVN information-based ARAS method, incorporating a new similarity measure and a hybrid subjective-objective weighting scheme (SVN-SOWIA), for sustainable EVCS site selection. In a later study, Arunodaya Mishra et al. [3] introduce a novel IPF-COPRAS method combining a new similarity measure, linear programming, and the COPRAS technique to select the optimal waste-to-energy technology for municipal solid waste treatment. Broumi et al. [19] developed new distance and similarity measures for IVNS based on geometric, set-theoretic, and matching function models. Their approach improves precision in measuring uncertainty and was validated through numerical comparisons. Pingping Chi [14] extends the TOPSIS method to INS by defining INS operations and distances and determining unknown attribute weights using the maximizing deviation method. Similarly, Zhang et al. [33] define operations, aggregation operators, and comparison approaches for INSs. Both approaches have been applied to the investment selection problem. Jun Ye [13] defined Hamming and Euclidean distances and developed similarity measures using INS values, which are applied to rank alternatives based on their closeness to an ideal solution for an investment decision problem involving four companies evaluated under risk, growth, and environmental impact criteria.

Said Broumi & Florentin Smarandache [20] proposed a novel CSM for IVNS based on Bhattacharya's distance, treating IVNS as vectors in 3D space. Comparative analysis and a pattern recognition example demonstrate its simplicity, robustness, and effectiveness over existing measures. Eda Bolturk and Cengiz Kahraman [9] proposed an IVN-AHP method utilizing CSM to objectively handle pairwise comparisons under uncertainty. Their approach was effectively applied to alternative energy selection. Zikang Lu & Jun Ye et al. [34] propose three CSMs for neutrosophic cubic sets based on vector angle, distance, and cosine functions and explore their mathematical properties and validation through an investment selection example. Radha et al. [16] introduced NPS with dependent components and developed improved correlation coefficients to analyze their relationships. Antony Crispin Sweety [1] proposed FNS and established algebraic and set-theoretic properties, thereby enhancing their applicability in complex decision-making environments. Said Broumi et al. [21] developed IVFNSs to effectively manage uncertainty and partial ignorance in complex evaluations. The study applied the IVFN-TOPSIS method to a numerical case of faculty performance evaluation, utilized score and accuracy functions, and accurately ranked alternatives in uncertain decision environments. Radha et al. [17] introduced cosine and cotangent similarity measures for FNSs, and the method was effectively applied in pattern recognition and medical diagnosis. Bhuvaneshwari et al. [7] introduced a novel distance measure tailored for FNS, enhancing decision-making accuracy by accounting for false membership and comparing six distance metrics.

Although several similarity measures exist for IFS, IVIFS, PFS, and FNS, limited work has been done on developing CSMs specifically for IVFNS. To address this gap, this study introduces three novel CSMs designed for the IVFNS environment. These measures are embedded into a TOPSIS-based MCDM framework under the IVFNS environment. To enhance flexibility, weighted extensions of the proposed similarity measures are developed. The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 provides the mathematical preliminaries of the paper, Section 3 details the proposed CSM for IVNFS, and Section 4 presents the application of the similarity measures validated using real-world case studies, including pattern recognition and medical diagnosis. Section 5 introduces the TOPSIS-based decision-making approach under the IVFNS environment, applying the proposed methodology to investment decision-making. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the core findings and concludes the study.

2. Prerequisites

Definition 2.1. [1] Consider a non-empty set \check{Z} . A FNS is defined on \check{Z} can be, structured as follows:

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$$\check{F} = \{(\check{z}, \xi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}), \zeta_{\check{F}}(\check{z}), \pi_{\check{F}}(\check{z})) \mid \check{z} \in \check{Z}\},$$

where $\xi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}), \zeta_{\check{F}}(\check{z}), \pi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}) \in [0, 1]$, denotes the degree of membership, non-membership and indeterminacy. Then $0 \leq (\xi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{F}}(\check{z}))^3 + (\pi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}))^3 \leq 2$. for all $\check{z} \in \check{Z}$.

Theorem 2.2. [17] Let $\check{F} = \{(\check{z}, \xi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}), \zeta_{\check{F}}(\check{z}), \pi_{\check{F}}(\check{z})) \mid \check{z} \in \check{Z}\}$ and $\check{G} = \{(\check{z}, \xi_{\check{G}}(\check{z}), \zeta_{\check{G}}(\check{z}), \pi_{\check{G}}(\check{z})) \mid \check{z} \in \check{Z}\}$ are two FNSs in the finite universe of discourse \check{Z} , then the CSM between them is defined as follows,

- (a) $0 \leq \mathcal{CS}_{FNS}(\check{F}, \check{G}) \leq 1$
- (b) $\mathcal{CS}_{FNS}(\check{F}, \check{G}) = 1 \Leftrightarrow \check{F} = \check{G}$
- (c) $\mathcal{CS}_{FNS}(\check{F}, \check{G}) = \mathcal{CS}_{FNS}(\check{G}, \check{F})$

Definition 2.3. [21] An IVFNS $\check{F} = \{(\check{z}_j, [\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)])\}$ on a nonempty set \check{Z} , where $\xi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j) = [\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)] \in [0, 1]$ denotes the interval-valued membership degree, $\zeta_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j) = [\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)] \in [0, 1]$ denotes the interval-valued non membership degree and $\pi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j) = [\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)] \in [0, 1]$ denotes the interval-valued indeterminacy degree, satisfying $0 \leq \xi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j)^3 + \zeta_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j)^3 \leq 1$ and $0 \leq \pi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j)^3 \leq 1$, $0 \leq \xi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j)^3 + \zeta_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j)^3 + \pi_{\check{F}}(\check{z}_j)^3 \leq 2$, for every $\check{z}_j \in \check{Z}$.

3. IVFNS - Cosine Similarity Measure

In this section we propose three CSMs between IVFNSs over the universal set \check{Z} .

Definition 3.1. Let $\check{Z} = \{\check{z}_1, \check{z}_2, \dots, \check{z}_j\}$ be a finite universe of discourse and $\check{F} = \{(\check{z}_j, [\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j)]) \mid \check{z}_j \in \check{Z}\}$ and $\check{G} = \{(\check{z}_j, [\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)]) \mid \check{z}_j \in \check{Z}\}$ be two IVFNSs. Then

1 . IVFNS - Cosine angle between two vectors

$$\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}(\check{F}, \check{G}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left[\frac{[(\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] + [(\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] + [(\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3]}{\sqrt{((\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2} \cdot \sqrt{((\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2} \right] \tag{1}$$

2 . IVFNS - Cosine measure based on distance

$$\mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left\{ \cos \left(\frac{ \left| (\xi_{\check{F}}^L(z_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^L(z_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(z_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(z_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(z_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(z_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(z_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(z_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\pi_{\check{F}}^L(z_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^L(z_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(z_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(z_j))^3 \right| }{12} \right) \pi \right\} \quad (2)$$

3 . IVFNS - Cosine measure based on cosine function

$$\mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = \frac{1}{3n(\sqrt{2}-1)} \sum_{j=1}^n \left\{ \left[\sqrt{2} \cos \left(\frac{ (\xi_{\check{F}}^L(z_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(z_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^L(z_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(z_j))^3 }{8} \right) \pi - 1 \right] + \left[\sqrt{2} \cos \left(\frac{ (\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(z_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(z_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(z_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(z_j))^3 }{8} \right) \pi - 1 \right] + \left[\sqrt{2} \cos \left(\frac{ (\pi_{\check{F}}^L(z_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(z_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^L(z_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(z_j))^3 }{8} \right) \pi - 1 \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

Theorem 3.2. *The proposed three CSM $\mathcal{CS}_{\kappa-IVFNS}(\check{F}, \check{G})$, where $\kappa = 1, 2, 3$ satisfies the following properties:*

- (a) $0 \preceq \mathcal{CS}_{\kappa-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) \preceq 1$
- (b) $\mathcal{CS}_{\kappa-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = 1 \Leftrightarrow \check{\mathcal{F}} = \check{\mathcal{G}}$
- (c) $\mathcal{CS}_{\kappa-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = \mathcal{CS}_{\kappa-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{F}})$

Proof. To prove Theorem 3.2, we verify that each of the proposed cosine similarity measures $\mathcal{CS}_{\kappa-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}})$, for $\kappa = 1, 2, 3$, satisfies the three stated properties. The proof is structured in three parts, corresponding to the three definitions of cosine similarity.

1. IVFNS - Cosine angle between two vectors

$$\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}})$$

- (a) Let $\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}$ be two IVFNS $\in [0, 1]$. The CSM between the vectors $\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{ \langle \check{\mathcal{F}}_j, \check{\mathcal{G}}_j \rangle }{ \| \check{\mathcal{F}}_j \| \cdot \| \check{\mathcal{G}}_j \| }$$

By the Cauchy Schwartz inequality, for any IVFNS vectors, $\check{\mathcal{F}}_j$, and $\check{\mathcal{G}}_j$ the following inequality holds,

$$\langle \check{\mathcal{F}}_j, \check{\mathcal{G}}_j \rangle \leq \| \check{\mathcal{F}}_j \| \cdot \| \check{\mathcal{G}}_j \|$$

Based on the above inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\begin{aligned} & [(\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \\ & + [(\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \\ & + [(\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \end{aligned} \right] \\ & \leq \left[\begin{aligned} & \sqrt{((\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2} \\ & \sqrt{((\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2} \end{aligned} \right] \\ & \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, it holds that $\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) \preceq 1$. Since all the components are lie in the interval $[0, 1]$, and are non negative thus the inequality, $\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{H}}) \succeq 0$. Hence $0 \preceq \mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) \preceq 1$.

(b) If $\check{\mathcal{F}} = \check{\mathcal{G}}$, then

$$\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j).$$

Hence $\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = 1$ holds.

(c) It is Straight forward.

2. IVFNS - Cosine measure based on distance

(a) However since, the components of IVFNS, $[\xi_{\check{F}}^L, \xi_{\check{F}}^U], [\zeta_{\check{F}}^L, \zeta_{\check{F}}^U], [\pi_{\check{F}}^L, \pi_{\check{F}}^U] \in [0, 1]$.

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq & \left[\frac{1}{12} \left(\left| (\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| \right. \right. \\ & + \left| (\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| \\ & \left. \left. + \left| (\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| \right) \right] \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that the cosine function satisfies

$$-1 \leq \cos(\theta) \leq 1, \quad \forall \theta \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Thus

$$0 \leq \cos \left[\frac{1}{12} \left(\left| (\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| + \left| (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 \right| \right) \right] \pi \leq 1$$

Therefore $0 \leq \mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) \leq 1$

(b) If $\check{\mathcal{F}} = \check{\mathcal{G}}$, then

$$\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j).$$

Hence $\mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = 1$ holds.

(c) By symmetry, $\mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = \mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{F}})$ holds.

3. IVFNS - Cosine measure based on cosine function

(a) Let $\rho_1 = \left(\frac{\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) + \xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) - \xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j) - \xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)}{2} \right)$, $\rho_2 = \left(\frac{\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) + \zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) - \zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j) - \zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)}{2} \right)$, $\rho_3 = \left(\frac{\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) + \pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) - \pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j) - \pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)}{2} \right)$. We have $-1 \preceq \cos(\rho_k) \preceq 1$ for $k = 1, 2, 3$. Thus $\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \preceq \cos(\frac{\pi}{4}\rho_k) \preceq 1$, then $0 \preceq \frac{1}{3n(\sqrt{2}-1)}((\sqrt{2} \cos(\frac{\pi}{8}\rho_k) - 1)) \preceq 1$. Therefore there exists $0 \preceq \mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) \preceq 1$.

(b) If $\check{\mathcal{F}} = \check{\mathcal{G}}$, then $\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j)$, $\xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)$, $\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j)$, $\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)$, $\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j) = \pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j)$, $\pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j) = \pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j)$. Hence $\mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{H}}) = 1$ holds.

(c) Cosine similarity is symmetric. Therefore $\mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = \mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{F}})$.

□

Example 3.3. Let $\check{\mathcal{Z}} = \{\varrho_1, \varrho_2, \varrho_3, \varrho_4\}$, and consider two IVFNSs,

$$\check{\mathcal{F}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\varrho_1, \langle [0.35, 0.41], [0.40, 0.50], [0.20, 0.32] \rangle), \\ (\varrho_2, \langle [0.25, 0.40], [0.31, 0.35], [0.22, 0.65] \rangle), \\ (\varrho_3, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.25, 0.40], [0.41, 0.52] \rangle), \\ (\varrho_4, \langle [0.20, 0.50], [0.35, 0.38], [0.20, 0.30] \rangle) \end{array} \right\}$$

and

$$\check{\mathcal{G}} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\varrho_1, \langle [0.18, 0.42], [0.40, 0.50], [0.20, 0.32] \rangle), \\ (\varrho_2, \langle [0.15, 0.35], [0.15, 0.35], [0.12, 0.45] \rangle), \\ (\varrho_3, \langle [0.54, 0.60], [0.25, 0.40], [0.32, 0.55] \rangle), \\ (\varrho_4, \langle [0.15, 0.60], [0.12, 0.45], [0.10, 0.20] \rangle) \end{array} \right\}$$

then the similarity between the sets $\check{\mathcal{F}}$ & $\check{\mathcal{G}}$ has been evaluated using three distinct cosine-based measures.

- (1) The CSM between two vectors, as defined in equation 1, is given by $\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = 0.979$.
- (2) Employing the distance-based cosine formulation from equation 2, the measure is slightly higher, resulting in $\mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = 0.999$.
- (3) Furthermore, using the cosine-function-based approach as defined in equation 3, the computed similarity is $\mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = 0.998$.

3.1. Weighted Cosine similarity measure under IVFNS

Let $\check{\mathcal{Z}} = \{\check{z}_1, \check{z}_2, \dots, \check{z}_j\}$ be a finite universe of discourse and consider two IVFNS $\check{\mathcal{F}} = \{\{\check{z}_j, [\xi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j), \xi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\pi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j)]\} : \check{z}_j \in \check{\mathcal{Z}}\}$ and $\check{\mathcal{G}} = \{\{\check{z}_j, [\xi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j), \xi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j), \zeta_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j)], [\pi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j), \pi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j)]\} : \check{z}_j \in \check{\mathcal{Z}}\}$, then $\omega_j = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) is the weight vector, the weight vector must adhere the following $0 \preceq \omega_j \preceq 1$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j = 1$. The weighted cosine measures of $CS_{IVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}})$ between $\check{\mathcal{F}}$ and $\check{\mathcal{G}}$ is given as

1 . Weighted CIF Cosine angle between two vectors

$$\mathcal{CS}_{1-WIVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j \left[\frac{[(\xi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\xi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] + [(\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] + [(\pi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3] \cdot [(\pi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3]}{\sqrt{((\xi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\pi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2} \cdot \sqrt{((\xi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2 + ((\pi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3)^2} \right] \quad (4)$$

2 . Weighted IVFNS Cosine measure based on distance

$$\mathcal{CS}_{2-WIVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j \left\{ \cos \left(\frac{ |(\xi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3| + |(\xi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3| + |(\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3| + |(\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3| + |(\pi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3| + |(\pi_{\check{\mathcal{F}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{\mathcal{G}}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3|}{12} \right) \pi \right\} \quad (5)$$

3 . Weighted IVFNS Cosine measure based on cosine function

$$\mathcal{CS}_{3-WIVFNS}(\check{\mathcal{F}}, \check{\mathcal{G}}) =$$

Saranya M, Jayanthi, D, "Novel Cosine Similarity Measures for Interval-Valued Fermatean Neutrosophic Sets with TOPSIS-Based MCDM Applications"

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3n(\sqrt{2}-1)} \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j \left\{ \left[\sqrt{2} \cos \left(\frac{(\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3}{8} \right) \pi - 1 \right] \right. \\ & \quad + \left[\sqrt{2} \cos \left(\frac{(\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3}{8} \right) \pi - 1 \right] \\ & \quad \left. + \left[\sqrt{2} \cos \left(\frac{(\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 + (\pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_j))^3 - (\pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_j))^3}{8} \right) \pi - 1 \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Theorem 3.4. Consider any two IVFNSs $\check{\mathcal{G}}$ and $\check{\mathcal{H}}$. Therefore, the weighted CSM, $\mathcal{CS}_{k-IVFNS}^{\omega_j}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{H}})$ (where $k = 1, 2, 3$), satisfies the following conditions:

- (a) $0 \preceq \mathcal{CS}_{k-IVFNS}^{\omega_j}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{H}}) \preceq 1$
- (b) $\mathcal{CS}_{k-IVFNS}^{\omega_j}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{H}}) = 1 \Leftrightarrow \check{\mathcal{G}} = \check{\mathcal{H}}$
- (c) $\mathcal{CS}_{k-IVFNS}^{\omega_j}(\check{\mathcal{G}}, \check{\mathcal{H}}) = \mathcal{CS}_{k-IVFNS}^{\omega_j}(\check{\mathcal{H}}, \check{\mathcal{G}})$

Proof. Since $0 \preceq \omega_j \preceq 1$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j = 1$. Thus, the proof of the aforementioned theorem can be easily derived, and therefore, we will omit it here. □

4. Decision Making - IVFNS - Cosine similarity measures

This section extensively applies the proposed CSM under IVFNS environment and the results were also subjected to comparisons with those obtained from different SM in IVIFS, IVPFS, IVNS.

4.1. Proposed Methodology

Let $\check{\mathcal{Z}} = \{\check{z}_1, \check{z}_2, \dots, \check{z}_n\}$ be a finite universe of discourse. Assume that there are m patterns each expressed as an IVFNS, denoted by

$$\begin{aligned} \check{\mathcal{F}}_j = & \{ \langle \check{z}_1, [\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_1), \xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_1)], [\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_1), \zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_1)], [\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_1), \pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_1)] \rangle, \dots, \\ & \langle \check{z}_n, [\xi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_n), \xi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_n)], [\zeta_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_n), \zeta_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_n)], [\pi_{\check{F}}^L(\check{z}_n), \pi_{\check{F}}^U(\check{z}_n)] \rangle : \check{z}_1, \dots, \check{z}_n \in \check{\mathcal{Z}} \} \quad \text{where } j = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{aligned}$$

An unknown pattern $\check{\mathcal{G}}$ is also represented as an IVFNS,

$$\begin{aligned} \check{\mathcal{G}} = & \{ \langle \check{z}_1, [\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_1), \xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_1)], [\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_1), \zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_1)], [\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_1), \pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_1)] \rangle, \dots, \\ & \langle \check{z}_n, [\xi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_n), \xi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_n)], [\zeta_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_n), \zeta_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_n)], [\pi_{\check{G}}^L(\check{z}_n), \pi_{\check{G}}^U(\check{z}_n)] \rangle : \check{z}_1, \dots, \check{z}_n \in \check{\mathcal{Z}} \} \end{aligned}$$

The pattern recognition process involves comparing the unknown pattern $\check{\mathcal{G}}$ with each known pattern $\check{\mathcal{F}}_j$, then the procedure is structured as follows

- Step 1.** For criterion $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, then the IVFNS decision matrix (DM) is constructed based on the evaluations of the alternatives $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ as provided by

the decision maker, and is represented as follows:

$$DM = \begin{matrix} & \check{z}_1 & \check{z}_2 & \check{z}_3 & \cdots & \check{z}_n \\ \check{F}_1 & \left(\begin{matrix} \check{\chi}_{11} & \check{\chi}_{12} & \check{\chi}_{13} & \cdots & \check{\chi}_{1n} \\ \check{\chi}_{21} & \check{\chi}_{22} & \check{\chi}_{23} & \cdots & \check{\chi}_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \check{\chi}_{m1} & \check{\chi}_{m2} & \check{\chi}_{m3} & \cdots & \check{\chi}_{mn} \end{matrix} \right) \\ \check{F}_2 & & & & & \\ \vdots & & & & & \\ \check{F}_m & & & & & \end{matrix}$$

Step 2. For each $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$, compute the IVFN - CSM, $\mathcal{CS}_{k-IVFNS}(\check{F}_j, \check{G})$.

Step 3. Determine $\arg \max_{1 \leq j \leq m} (\mathcal{CS}_{k-IVFNS}(\check{F}_j, \check{G}))$. Assigning the unknown pattern \check{G} to the pattern \check{F}_j .

4.2. Illustrative Example - Pattern Recognition

Example 4.1. Examine four patterns ($i= 1, 2, 3, 4$) in which corresponding features are indicated by IVFNS as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \check{F}_1 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.25, 0.35], [0.3, 0.5], [0.1, 0.4] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.35, 0.40], [0.30, 0.35], [0.15, 0.70] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.40, 0.55], [0.40, 0.40], [0.30, 0.55] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.20, 0.60], [0.35, 0.40], [0.10, 0.50] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_2 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.25, 0.35], [0.45, 0.60], [0.15, 0.45] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.15, 0.55], [0.35, 0.45], [0.10, 0.80] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.25, 0.50], [0.30, 0.45], [0.20, 0.45] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.40, 0.60], [0.35, 0.50], [0.15, 0.50] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_3 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.15, 0.35], [0.45, 0.55], [0.15, 0.35] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.25, 0.60], [0.18, 0.35], [0.25, 0.70] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.35, 0.45], [0.25, 0.40], [0.12, 0.60] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.45, 0.60], [0.35, 0.45], [0.25, 0.35] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_4 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.25, 0.35], [0.42, 0.60], [0.25, 0.45] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.45, 0.55], [0.25, 0.45], [0.20, 0.55] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.45, 0.50], [0.10, 0.50], [0.30, 0.55] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.35, 0.65], [0.25, 0.45], [0.38, 0.40] \rangle)\} \end{aligned}$$

Further there is an unknown pattern \check{G} which is to be categorized as,

$$\begin{aligned} \check{G} &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.12, 0.35], [0.45, 0.55], [0.10, 0.35] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.35, 0.45], [0.15, 0.25], [0.40, 0.55] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.15, 0.40], [0.35, 0.60] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.12, 0.55], [0.30, 0.40], [0.15, 0.35] \rangle)\} \end{aligned}$$

Estimate the CSM between $\check{F}_i (i = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ and \check{G} . The objective is to categorize pattern \check{G} into one of the known patterns $\check{F}_1, \check{F}_2, \check{F}_3, \check{F}_4$.

The proposed CSM $\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}$, $\mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}$ & $\mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}$ for IVFNS consistently identified the unknown pattern \check{G} , categorizing it with \check{F}_3 . The numerical outcomes presented in Tables 2 & 3 demonstrate that the proposed measures outperform existing classical approaches such as IVIFS, IVPFS, and IVNS for pattern recognition in uncertain IVFNS environments. This superiority is further supported by the visual comparison shown in Figure 1.

TABLE 2. Proposed Measures Results - Pattern Recognition

Similarity Measures	$S(\check{F}_1, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_2, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_3, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_4, \check{G})$	Pattern Recognition results
$CS_{1-IVFNS}$	0.967	0.962	0.980	0.951	\check{F}_3
$CS_{2-IVFNS}$	0.997	0.994	0.998	0.994	\check{F}_3
$CS_{3-IVFNS}$	0.996	0.995	0.998	0.994	\check{F}_3

TABLE 3. Pattern Recognition - Similarity Measure Comparison

Similarity Measures	$S(\check{F}_1, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_2, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_3, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_4, \check{G})$	Pattern Recognition results
$S_{Broumi-IVNS}$ [20]	0.982	0.976	0.984	0.981	\check{F}_3
$S_{Jun-1-IVNS}$ [13]	0.672	0.490	0.673	0.622	\check{F}_3
$S_{Jun-2-IVNS}$ [13]	0.767	0.691	0.784	0.770	\check{F}_3
$S_{R-IVPFS}$ [3]	0.910	0.878	0.924	0.900	\check{F}_3
$S_{S-IVIFS}$ [25]	0.980	0.966	0.99	0.99	\check{F}_3
$S_{D-IVIFS}$ [8]	0.724	0.728	0.738	0.663	\check{F}_3
$S_{PD-IVIFS}$ [15]	0.985	0.977	0.993	0.993	\check{F}_3

FIGURE 1. Pattern Recognition

4.3. Illustrative Example - Medical Diagnosis

Example 4.2. Consider a set of diseases $\check{F} = \{\check{F}_1(\text{viral fever}), \check{F}_2(\text{malaria}), \check{F}_3(\text{Stomachproblem}), \check{F}_4(\text{Typhoid})\}$ and $\check{S} = \{\varrho_1(\text{Temprature}), \varrho_2(\text{Headache}), \varrho_3(\text{StomachPain}), \varrho_4(\text{Cough})\}$ symbolize as the set of symptoms which are represented as in the form of IVFNSs as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \check{F}_1 = & \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.35, 0.41], [0.40, 0.50], [0.20, 0.32] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.25, 0.40], [0.31, 0.35], [0.22, 0.65] \rangle), \\ & (\varrho_3, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.25, 0.40], [0.41, 0.52] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.20, 0.50], [0.35, 0.38], [0.20, 0.30] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_2 = & \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.20, 0.40], [0.50, 0.60], [0.20, 0.40] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.15, 0.50], [0.35, 0.40], [0.20, 0.70] \rangle), \\ & (\varrho_3, \langle [0.40, 0.50], [0.30, 0.35], [0.40, 0.50] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.45, 0.50], [0.35, 0.40], [0.20, 0.50] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_3 = & \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.15, 0.35], [0.50, 0.60], [0.20, 0.40] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.20, 0.60], [0.20, 0.40], [0.40, 0.60] \rangle), \\ & (\varrho_3, \langle [0.30, 0.50], [0.20, 0.50], [0.20, 0.60] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.45, 0.50], [0.35, 0.45], [0.35, 0.40] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_4 = & \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.10, 0.20], [0.40, 0.60], [0.20, 0.45] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.35, 0.45], [0.15, 0.20], [0.40, 0.50] \rangle), \\ & (\varrho_3, \langle [0.45, 0.65], [0.30, 0.35], [0.25, 0.55] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.40, 0.50], [0.30, 0.40], [0.40, 0.50] \rangle)\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \check{G} = & \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.18, 0.40], [0.40, 0.50], [0.20, 0.32] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.25, 0.30], [0.20, 0.30], [0.12, 0.45] \rangle), \\ & (\varrho_3, \langle [0.54, 0.6], [0.25, 0.40], [0.32, 0.55] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.15, 0.60], [0.12, 0.40], [0.10, 0.20] \rangle)\} \end{aligned}$$

This illustrative example presents a medical diagnosis problem using the proposed CSM for IVFNSs, aimed at identifying the disease of a patient \check{G} among four possible diagnoses \check{F}_1 , \check{F}_2 , \check{F}_3 , and \check{F}_4 . Each diagnosis corresponds to a specific disease, and the analysis is based on four symptoms ($\check{z}_1, \check{z}_2, \check{z}_3, \check{z}_4$) exhibited by the patient.

TABLE 4. Proposed Measures Results - Medical Diagnosis

Similarity Measures	$S(\check{F}_1, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_2, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_3, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_4, \check{G})$	Diagnosed results
$\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}$	0.981	0.958	0.932	0.913	\check{F}_1
$\mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}$	0.999	0.996	0.995	0.998	\check{F}_1
$\mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}$	0.999	0.996	0.997	0.998	\check{F}_1

The results obtained from the proposed SM ($\mathcal{CS}_{1-IVFNS}, \mathcal{CS}_{2-IVFNS}, \mathcal{CS}_{3-IVFNS}$) were employed to compute the similarity degrees between the patient and each disease. All three measures consistently identified \check{F}_1 (Viral Fever) as the most probable diagnosis, as shown in Table 4. Furthermore, a comparative analysis with existing similarity measures IVIFS, IVPFS and IVFNS -based SM as shown in Table 5, reaffirmed the superior discriminating capability and reliability of the proposed approaches. The results validate that the developed CSMs

TABLE 5. Medical Diagnosis - Similarity Measure Comparison

Similarity Measures	$S(\check{F}_1, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_2, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_3, \check{G})$	$S(\check{F}_4, \check{G})$	Diagnosed results
$S_{Broumi-IVNS}$ [20]	0.991	0.990	0.984	0.965	\check{F}_1
$S_{Jun-1-IVNS}$ [13]	0.742	0.545	0.503	0.545	\check{F}_1
$S_{Jun-2-IVNS}$ [13]	0.815	0.718	0.688	0.709	\check{F}_1
$S_{R-IVPFS}$ [3]	0.943	0.876	0.865	0.897	\check{F}_1
$S_{S-IVIFS}$ [25]	0.996	0.994	0.991	0.977	\check{F}_1
$S_{D-IVIFS}$ [8]	0.732	0.722	0.708	0.713	\check{F}_1
$S_{PD-IVIFS}$ [15]	0.996	0.994	0.992	0.988	\check{F}_1

FIGURE 2. Medical Diagnosis

not only provide computational consistency but also enhance diagnostic accuracy in uncertain environments. The graphical representation in Figure 2 shows the effectiveness of the proposed measures and showed superior performance in medical diagnosis applications.

5. TOPSIS approach Based on cosine similarity measure under IVFNS

This segment introduces a TOPSIS methodology designed to tackle MCDM challenges by employing the CSM within the context of IVFNSs.

5.1. Problem Description

Let $\check{F} = \{\check{F}_1, \check{F}_2, \dots, \check{F}_m\}$ be the set of m alternatives and $\check{z} = \{\varrho_1, \varrho_2, \dots, \varrho_n\}$ be the set of n criteria labeled by IVFNSs $\check{F}_{ij} = (\zeta_{ij}, \lambda_{ij})$, where $\zeta_{ij} = \langle [\xi_{ij}^-, \xi_{ij}^+][\vartheta_{ij}^-, \vartheta_{ij}^+] \rangle$ and $\lambda_{i,j} = \langle \xi_{ij}, \vartheta_{ij} \rangle$ represent IVIFNs and IFNs.

5.1.1. Algorithm - TOPSIS Approach

Step 1. Construct the CIF - DM for each criterion $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ based on the evaluation of alternatives $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ is given by the decision maker represented as follows

$$DM = \begin{matrix} & \varrho_1 & \varrho_2 & \varrho_3 & \cdots & \varrho_n \\ \check{F}_1 & \check{\chi}_{11} & \check{\chi}_{12} & \check{\chi}_{13} & \cdots & \check{\chi}_{1n} \\ \check{F}_2 & \check{\chi}_{21} & \check{\chi}_{22} & \check{\chi}_{23} & \cdots & \check{\chi}_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \\ \check{F}_m & \check{\chi}_{m1} & \check{\chi}_{m2} & \check{\chi}_{m3} & \cdots & \check{\chi}_{mn} \end{matrix}$$

Step 2. Determine both IVFN - positive ideal solution \check{F}^+ and IVFN - negative ideal solution \check{F}^- corresponding to the alternative \check{F}_j are defined as follows:

$$\check{F}^+ = \langle \langle [\xi_{j+}^L, \xi_{j+}^U], [\zeta_{j+}^L, \zeta_{j+}^U], [\pi_{j+}^L, \pi_{j+}^U] \rangle \rangle$$

$$\check{F}^- = \langle \langle [\xi_{j-}^L, \xi_{j-}^U], [\zeta_{j-}^L, \zeta_{j-}^U], [\pi_{j-}^L, \pi_{j-}^U] \rangle \rangle$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \langle [\xi_{j+}^L, \xi_{j+}^U], [\zeta_{j+}^L, \zeta_{j+}^U], [\pi_{j+}^L, \pi_{j+}^U] \rangle \rangle \\ &= \langle \langle [\max_i(\xi_{ij}^L), \max_i(\xi_{ij}^U)], [\min_i(\zeta_{ij}^L), \min_i(\zeta_{ij}^U)], [\min_i(\pi_{ij}^L), \min_i(\pi_{ij}^U)] \rangle \rangle \\ & \langle \langle [\xi_{j-}^L, \xi_{j-}^U], [\zeta_{j-}^L, \zeta_{j-}^U], [\pi_{j-}^L, \pi_{j-}^U] \rangle \rangle \\ &= \langle \langle [\min_i(\xi_{ij}^L), \min_i(\xi_{ij}^U)], [\max_i(\zeta_{ij}^L), \max_i(\zeta_{ij}^U)], [\max_i(\pi_{ij}^L), \max_i(\pi_{ij}^U)] \rangle \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Step 3. Compute the proximity measures between the alternatives for both CIF - positive ideal solution $S_{IVFNS}(\check{F}_i, \check{F}^+)$ and CIF - negative ideal solution $S_{IVFNS}(\check{F}_i, \check{F}^-)$ between the alternatives \check{F}_j .

Step 4. Employ the closeness index for the decision matrix with respect to \check{F}^+ and \check{F}^- for an alternative \check{F}_j is determined as follows:

$$CC_i = \frac{CS_{1-IVFNS}(\check{F}_i, \check{F}^+)}{CS_{1-IVFNS}(\check{F}_i, \check{F}^+) + CS_{1-IVFNS}(\check{F}_i, \check{F}^-)}$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Step 5. Rank the alternatives based on the maximum degree of similarity. Conclude CC_i is the optimum choice.

5.2. Illustrative Example

The computations of the TOPSIS Method are implemented in the following steps by considering the decisions of the decision-maker to evaluate the alternatives.

5.2.1. Case Study - MCDM

A financial firm is considering investing a sum of money in one of five potential companies. They are (\check{F}_1) Technology Company, (\check{F}_2) Aerospace Company, (\check{F}_3) Finance Company, (\check{F}_4) Energy Company and (\check{F}_5) Automobile Company. The assessment criteria for the five alternatives are based on four distinct attributes: (ϱ_1) is Risk, (ϱ_2) is Growth Potential, (ϱ_3) is Environmental Impact and (ϱ_4) is Innovation. The decision-maker is asked to assess the five possible alternatives based on the four attributes using CIFNs. The subsequent steps of the proposed approach are implemented to identify the best company for investment employing IVFNSs as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \check{F}_1 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.10, 0.20], [0.30, 0.40] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.10, 0.40], [0.30, 0.40] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.60, 0.80], [0.10, 0.20], [0.10, 0.30] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.30, 0.40], [0.50, 0.60], [0.20, 0.30] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_2 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.60, 0.80], [0.10, 0.20], [0.20, 0.30] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.20, 0.40], [0.20, 0.30] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.60, 0.70], [0.10, 0.20], [0.20, 0.30] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.30, 0.40], [0.40, 0.50], [0.30, 0.40] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_3 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.20, 0.30], [0.10, 0.30] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.30, 0.40], [0.20, 0.50], [0.10, 0.20] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.30, 0.40], [0.30, 0.40] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.45, 0.55], [0.30, 0.40], [0.30, 0.30] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_4 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.60, 0.70], [0.10, 0.20], [0.20, 0.30] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.60, 0.70], [0.10, 0.20], [0.10, 0.40] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.50, 0.70], [0.20, 0.30], [0.30, 0.50] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.20, 0.40], [0.10, 0.20], [0.40, 0.50] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}_5 &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.40, 0.60], [0.30, 0.40], [0.30, 0.50] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.70, 0.80], [0.10, 0.20], [0.10, 0.20] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.70, 0.80], [0.20, 0.20], [0.10, 0.50] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.10, 0.20], [0.10, 0.20], [0.30, 0.40] \rangle)\} \end{aligned}$$

Further there is an ideal \check{F}^+ and \check{F}^- which is to be categorized as,

$$\begin{aligned} \check{F}^+ &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.60, 0.80], [0.10, 0.20], [0.10, 0.30] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.70, 0.80], [0.10, 0.20], [0.10, 0.20] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.70, 0.80], [0.10, 0.20], [0.10, 0.30] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.45, 0.55], [0.10, 0.20], [0.20, 0.30] \rangle)\} \\ \check{F}^- &= \{(\varrho_1, \langle [0.40, 0.60], [0.30, 0.40], [0.30, 0.50] \rangle), (\varrho_2, \langle [0.30, 0.40], [0.20, 0.50], [0.30, 0.40] \rangle), \\ &\quad (\varrho_3, \langle [0.50, 0.60], [0.30, 0.40], [0.30, 0.50] \rangle), (\varrho_4, \langle [0.10, 0.20], [0.50, 0.60], [0.40, 0.50] \rangle)\} \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 6. Closeness Coefficient Value

Alternatives (\check{F}_j)	\check{F}^+	\check{F}^-	CC_i
\check{F}_1	0.807	0.866	0.48
\check{F}_2	0.863	0.846	0.50
\check{F}_3	0.867	0.797	0.52
\check{F}_4	0.858	0.728	0.54
\check{F}_5	0.773	0.753	0.51

TABLE 7. TOPSIS - Similarity Measure Comparison Table

	Measure Value	Ranking	Optimum one
$S_{Broumi-IVNS}$ [20]	0.50,0.50,0.50,0.52,0.50	$\check{F}_1 = \check{F}_2 = \check{F}_3 = \check{F}_4 \succ \check{F}_5$	\check{F}_4
$S_{Jun-1-IVNS}$ [13]	0.52,0.56,0.51,0.63,0.62	$\check{F}_1 \prec \check{F}_2 \succ \check{F}_3 \prec \check{F}_4 \succ \check{F}_5$	\check{F}_4
$S_{Jun-2-IVNS}$ [13]	0.49,0.52,0.48,0.55,0.54	$\check{F}_1 \prec \check{F}_2 \succ \check{F}_3 \prec \check{F}_4 \succ \check{F}_5$	\check{F}_4
$S_{R-IVPFS}$ [3]	0.49,0.51,0.47,0.55,0.52	$\check{F}_1 \prec \check{F}_2 \succ \check{F}_3 \prec \check{F}_4 \succ \check{F}_5$	\check{F}_4
$S_{S-IVIFS}$ [25]	0.50,0.50,0.50,0.54,0.51	$\check{F}_1 = \check{F}_2 = \check{F}_3 \prec \check{F}_4 \succ \check{F}_5$	\check{F}_4
$S_{D-IVIFS}$ [8]	0.54,0.55,0.51,0.56,0.55	$\check{F}_1 \prec \check{F}_2 \succ \check{F}_3 \prec \check{F}_4 \succ \check{F}_5$	\check{F}_4
$S_{PD-IVIFS}$ [15]	0.50,0.50,0.49,0.53,0.51	$\check{F}_1 = \check{F}_2 \succ \check{F}_3 \prec \check{F}_4 \succ \check{F}_5$	\check{F}_4
Proposed	0.48,0.50,0.52,0.54,0.51	$\check{F}_1 \prec \check{F}_2 \prec \check{F}_3 \prec \check{F}_4 \succ \check{F}_5$	\check{F}_4

The values of the proposed CSMS and decision outcomes are obtained through the application of steps 2 and 3 of the TOPSIS method, as presented in Table 6, comparing the proposed approach with eight existing approaches under IVNS, IVPFS and IVIFS are presented in 7 . The tabulated results are subsequently visualized in graphical format, as depicted in Fig. 3. Furthermore, Table 7 indicates that several ranking results demonstrate consistency, with $CS_{1-IVFNS}(\check{F}_4)$ (Energy Company) emerging as the optimal choice, thus validating the efficacy of our approach. Consequently, the impact on alternative ranking underscores its significance in the proposed MCDM applications.

FIGURE 3. Comparison Diagram

5.3. Sensitivity Analysis via Leave-One-Out Method

To assess the robustness and stability of the proposed IVFNS-TOPSIS decision-making model, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis was carried out using the Leave-One-Out (LOO) method. This technique systematically excludes one criterion at a time from the decision matrix to examine its influence on the final ranking of alternatives. Let $D \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ be the original IVFNS decision matrix comprising $m = 5$ alternatives and $n = 4$ criteria: (ϱ_1) is Risk, (ϱ_2) is Growth Potential, (ϱ_3) is Environmental Impact and (ϱ_4) is Innovation. The proposed model applies a cosine similarity-based IVFNS aggregation followed by the TOPSIS ranking approach to compute the closeness coefficient CC_i for each alternative A_i .

Considering all decision criteria, the ranking sequence obtained was $\check{F}_4 > \check{F}_3 > \check{F}_5 > \check{F}_2 > \check{F}_1$, indicating that \check{F}_4 is the most preferred alternative. To perform Leave-One-Out analysis, reduced decision matrices $D_{(-j)}$, where $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$, were constructed by omitting one criterion \check{z}_j at a time. The IVFNS-TOPSIS method was then reapplied to compute new closeness coefficients $CC_i^{(-j)}$ and the resulting rankings. The analysis shows that omitting ϱ_1 , ϱ_3 , or ϱ_4 retains \check{F}_4 as the top-ranked alternative, while exclusion of ϱ_2 leads to \check{F}_3 emerging as the top choice. This indicates that the criterion ϱ_2 (Growth) has a relatively higher influence on the final decision outcome. Nevertheless, in three out of four Leave one out scenarios, \check{F}_4 remains the top alternative, demonstrating the robustness and stability of the proposed IVFNS-TOPSIS framework under partial criterion exclusion.

The Leave-One-Out sensitivity analysis reveals that the alternatives \check{F}_3 and \check{F}_4 consistently dominate the ranking positions across all exclusion scenarios. Specifically, \check{F}_4 retains the top

TABLE 8. Sensitivity Analysis: Ranking under Leave One Out Method

Removed Criterion	New Ranking Order	Top Alternative
ϱ_1 (Risk)	$\check{\mathcal{F}}_4 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_5 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_3 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_2 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_1$	$\check{\mathcal{F}}_4$
ϱ_2 (Growth)	$\check{\mathcal{F}}_3 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_4 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_2 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_5 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_1$	$\check{\mathcal{F}}_3$
ϱ_3 (Environment)	$\check{\mathcal{F}}_4 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_3 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_5 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_2 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_1$	$\check{\mathcal{F}}_4$
ϱ_4 (Innovation)	$\check{\mathcal{F}}_4 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_2 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_5 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_5 > \check{\mathcal{F}}_1$	$\check{\mathcal{F}}_4$

rank in three out of four Leave-One-Out configurations, while $\check{\mathcal{F}}_3$ ascends to the first position only when the growth criterion ϱ_2 is excluded. This persistence of top-ranking performance by $\check{\mathcal{F}}_4$, coupled with the stable presence of $\check{\mathcal{F}}_3$ in the top two, affirms the robustness of the proposed IVFNS-TOPSIS method under partial data perturbation. Moreover, the low sensitivity to individual criterion exclusion demonstrates the model’s stability and applicability in uncertain and interval-valued MCDM environments.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we introduced three novel CSMs for IVFNS, formulated using vector-based, distance-based, and cosine-function-based approaches, and established mathematical properties of these measures to ensure their theoretical robustness. Furthermore, we developed weighted measures of each CSM and proposed a TOPSIS-based MCDM framework under an IVFNS environment. To validate the practical utility of the proposed measures was demonstrated through real-world challenges such as pattern recognition, medical diagnosis, and international investments of the start-ups. Comparative analysis with existing similarity measures confirmed that our proposed methods exhibit accuracy and reliability in environments characterized by uncertainty and vagueness.

This research addresses a significant gap in the existing literature, as CSM within the framework of IVFNS has remained unexplored. The proposed methodology not only contributes new theoretical frameworks but also demonstrates strong practical applicability across multiple domains. However, the framework assumes precise expert-defined interval values and static decision environments, which may limit its robustness in highly dynamic or uncertain scenarios. In future work, we aim to extend these similarity measures to more complex environments, such as q-rung orthopair neutrosophic sets and cubic Fermatean neutrosophic environments, and further explore their integration into hybrid decision-making models.

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